

EMPOWERING WEAVERS: TRAINING ON WORKERS COMMITMENT IN HANDLOOM WEAVING COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES

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Abstract

The handloom industry in India is renowned for its exceptional craftsmanship, reflecting the vibrant Indian culture through exquisite hand spinning, weaving, and printing skills. Predominantly household-based, this industry spans thousands of towns and villages, with skills passed down through generations. The sector has employed many artisans from rural and semi-urban areas, including many women and economically disadvantaged individuals. It benefits from inexpensive and plentiful labor, local resource utilization, low capital investment, unique craftsmanship, and increasing international recognition. Despite these strengths, the industry represents only a small fraction of Indian exports, necessitating efforts to promote and channelize its offerings. A study conducted in Kerala, known for its deep-rooted connection with the handloom industry, highlights the sector's role as a major employment source, second only to the coir sector. The industry is predominantly cooperative, covering 98.4% of total looms. The study's model, with an SRMR value of 0.023 and an NFI of 0.937, indicates a good fit. Path coefficient values show a positive effect of workers' training on satisfaction (0.944) and commitment (0.312), with R^2 values is of 0.892 and 0.954, respectively. Effective training in handloom weaving cooperative societies enhances workers' satisfaction and commitment, contributing to organizational success and personal development.

Keywords: Handloom Weaving Cooperative Societies, Workers Satisfaction, Workers Commitment, Workers Training, Individual Development, Organisational Growth, Human Resource Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

India's handloom industry is renowned for its rich tradition of exceptional craftsmanship, which reflects and preserves the vibrant Indian culture (Roy & et.al 2024). Indian artisans are globally recognized for their exquisite hand spinning, weaving, and printing skills (Dutta, M. 2023). This industry is predominantly household-based, with family members collaboratively contributing to production (Hirshman, A. J. 2020). These activities span thousands of towns and villages across the country, with skills being passed down through generations (Hareven, T. K.2018). The sector has provides employment to numerous artisans from rural and semi-urban areas, including many women and individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds (Yadav & et.al 2024). The industry's key strengths include access to the inexpensive and abundant labors, the use of locally resources, low capital investment, unique craftsmanship, and increasing the international recognition (Datta, D. B., &

Bhattacharyya, S.2016). Despite its unique characteristics, the industry accounts for only a small portion of Indian exports in the global markets, underscoring the need for initiatives to a promote and channel its offering to unlock its hidden potentials (Kotabe, M., & Kothari, T.2016).

Given the disadvantages faced by the handloom sector in India, adopting Human Resource Management (HRM) practices can help address various issues and improve the economic conditions of weavers (Laha, A., & Ghosh, S. K. (2021). HR functions play a crucial role in supporting staff, motivating line workers, and achieving organizational goals (Mahapatro, B. (2021). Effective HR policies and procedures can be boost employees motivation and engagements, potentially altering attitudes and resolving cognitive dissonances (Hinojosa & et al., 2017). Despite the unorganized sector's lack of a formal HR framework, establishing and standardizing such policies is challenging but feasible (Thite & et al., 2014). In 2004, the Government of India acknowledged the significance of the sector by setting up the National Commission for the Enterprises in the Unorganized Sectors (NCEUS) (Saxena, 2009). Four years later, in the 2008, NCEUS presented a report title "Report on Definitional and Statistical Issues Relating to the Informal Economy," which can be found on the Development Commissioner MSME website. According to the report, the unorganized by sector includes all unincorporated privates enterprises owned by individuals or households that are involved in the production and sale of good and services. These enterprises operate on a proprietary or partnership basis and employ fewer than ten workers (Kumar, 2021). The National Accounts Statistic (NAS) defines the unorganized sector as comprising all operational units that are not governed by any statutory act or legal provision and do not keep regular accounts (Rao, 2021). The lack of regular accounts is a primary criterion for classifying these units as unorganized, posing a significant challenge for HR in defining and implementing policies and procedures (Veluchamy & et al., 2021). Despite these challenges, the government is taking initiatives to develop and sustain the handloom sector. Various NGOs, government boards, and the Ministry of Textiles are working to support this sector (Bhowmik, 2021). The Government of the India has set up multiple Handloom Boards to the manage production, export, and import activities, implement effective schemes, and allocate necessary funds to the support the growth of the handloom industry (Wanniarachchi & et al., 2021). These boards comprises the All-India 'Handloom Board', 'Cotton Advisory Board', 'Central Wool Development Board', 'Jute Advisory Board', and 'Central Silk Board'.

1.1 Important of handlooms in Kerala:

The handloom sector in Kerala directly and indirectly employs around 1.75 lakh people, making it the second-largest traditional industry in the state after the coir sector. The handloom industry is mainly centered in the districts of Thiruvananthapuram, Kannur, Kozhikode, Palakkad, Ernakulam, Thrissur, Kollam, and Kasargode. Kerala's Kasavu sarees are widely admired by women throughout India for their fine count, natural colors, texture, and golden borders. Kerala is also famous for its cotton handloom fabrics produced in Kannur, Vadagara, and

Kozhikode, which are popular in export markets. Balaramapuram in the Thiruvananthapuram district holds historical significance as one of the oldest handloom centers in the state. The primary weavers here are the Chaliyas community, who migrated from Nagercoil and Tirunelveli in Tamil Nadu around 250 years ago during the reign of Balaramavarma, the ruler of Travancore. Kuthampully in the Thrissur district is another renowned handloom center, where the Devangas community, who migrated from Karnataka around 500 years ago under the patronage of the Kochi Royal family, are actively engaged in weaving. Chennamangalam in the Ernakulam district is another significant handloom center, renowned for producing Double Dhoti, Mundu, and Neriyathu.

This study seeks to explore the effect of the employee training on employee commitment within the handloom weaving cooperative societies in Kerala, which are crucial to the country's export sector. The research focuses on reviewing various training methods employed by these cooperative societies. Although the cost of employee training is high, it is considerably lower than the potential profits that can be achieved through effective training programs. Many cooperative societies face challenges such as absenteeism, high turnover rates, lack of commitment, low motivation, and insufficient knowledge and skills among employees. This study addresses these issues by identifying the problems affecting employee commitment and evaluating the shortcomings of current training programs. It also proposes solutions to enhance training effectiveness and improve employee commitment in handloom weaving cooperative societies.

1.2 Statement of the problem:

Employee training is crucial for organizational success. Problems often arise from a lack of training, ineffective programs, or poor implementation (Tembo, E. M.2012). Management must provide training on self-monitoring and personality development (Danish & et al., 2013). Research highlights training as vital for effective human resource management. Key principles include meaningful inputs, efficiency, employee differences, and continuous development (Diab & Ajlouni, 2015). Training programs aim to equip employees with necessary information and skills for professional growth (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). These skills help employees collaborate to achieve organizational goals (Truitt, 2011). In a competitive, globalized, and technologically advanced business environment, employee knowledge and skills are essential for performance and competitiveness (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Employee commitment, shown through loyalty and productivity, is linked to positive outcomes like retention, attendance, achievement, quality work, and organizational performance (Porter & et al., 1974; Rabinowitz & Hall, 1977; Randall, 1990). Therefore, providing training to develop employee knowledge and skills is crucial for fostering commitment and achieving organizational success.

1.3 Need for the study:

Employee commitment and training are closely linked. When employees are satisfied with their job profiles, company practices, and possess the necessary skills, they tend

to feel more committed to their jobs and stay with the company for the long term (Kehoe, R. R., & Wright, P. M.2013). Conversely, if their performance is lacking or there are no opportunities for career advancement within the organization, they may seek alternatives (Kraimer & et. al 2011). A lack of employee commitment can lead to various administrative, operational, and financial issues (Singh, A. 2022). A study by Awino Molly (2020) concluded that employee commitment can be enhanced through proper training, and managers should focus on addressing their training needs. The study also found that the reward system moderates the relationship between career training and employee commitment. Training boosts an employee's confidence in their skills and knowledge, which in turn improves their commitment to the organization (Ocen & et. al 2017). Although extensive research have been done on the impact of the training with employee performance, the role of training in boosting employee commitment remains underexplored (Solangi & et.al 2022). Organizations may not fully recognize that training can significantly influence employee commitment (Nauman & et. al 2021). This research gap highlights the need for a study on the impact of training on employee commitment, specifically within handloom weaving cooperative societies in Kerala.

Figure 1: India's handloom export trend

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The relationship between employee training and commitment has been extensively studied in various journals. For instance, Gan and Yusof (2019) in their review paper highlighted that effective training programs significantly contribute to employee retention and commitment. They found that when employees perceive training as beneficial, it enhances their loyalty and commitment to the organization. In a similar

vein, 'Bashir and Long' (2015) investigated the relationship between training and organizational commitment among the academicians in the Malaysia, finding that training has a positive impact on both affective and normative commitments. They emphasized that support from co-workers and supervisors during training plays a crucial role in fostering commitment (Rawashdeh, A. M., & Tamimi, S. A.2020). These studies underscore the importance of investing in comprehensive training programs to boost employee commitment and organizational success.

The literature on training and employee commitment highlights the significant impact of training programs on enhancing employee commitment and organizational performance (Nauman & et.al 20221). Studies indicate that effective training programs not only improve employees' skills and knowledge but also foster a sense of the loyalty and commitment to organization (Mampuru & et.al 2024). Research shows that effective training programs not only enhance employees' skills and the knowledge but also cultivate a sense of the loyalty and commitment to the organization (Mampuru & et.al 2024).For instance, research has shown that when employees perceive training as beneficial and aligned with their career goals, their commitment to the organization increases (Morrow, P. C.2011). Additionally, training that focuses on personal development and leadership skills can lead to higher levels of employee engagement and motivation (Chua & et.al 2021). Overall, the literature suggests that investing in comprehensive training programs is crucial for organizations aiming to boost employee commitment and achieve long-term success. 'Kasimu Sendawula & et. al (2018)' found that training and the employee engagement are significant predictors of employee performance, with training accounting for 44.7% of the variance in performance. Eli Ayawo Atatsi & et.al (2019) conducted a review that synthesized literature on organizational citizenship behavior, leader-member exchange, learning, innovative work behavior, and employee performance. They identified positive relationships between these behaviors and employee performance. Hartini & et al. (2022) and Najeed & et al. (2022) conducted a the systematic review on factors influencing the employee performance, aiming to provide an accurate synthesis of relevant literature while minimizing bias and analytical errors.

2.1 Theoretical background:

Social Exchange theory posits that relationships are built on reciprocal exchanges. In the context of employee training, when organizations invest in training, employees feel valued and are likely to reciprocate with increased loyalty and commitment (Cropanzano.R & et. al 2017).

H1: Worker's training has a positive effect on workers commitment.

Social Identity Theory suggests that employees derive part of their identity from their organization. Training can enhance this identification by aligning personal and organizational goals, leading to higher commitment (Liu & et. Al 2013). Research indicates that effective training programs can significantly boost organizational commitment (Rawashdeh, A. M., & Tamimi, S. A. (2020). Employees who undergo

regular training tend to feel more valued and engaged, resulting in higher levels of affective and normative commitment (Albrecht, S & et. al 2015).

H2: Worker's training has a positive effect on workers satisfaction.

Studies have shown that effective training programs can significantly boost job satisfaction and commitment (Ahamd, H. (2023). Training enhances employees' skills and knowledge, making them feel more competent and valued, which in turn increases their satisfaction and commitment to the organization (Ensour & et. al 2018).

H3: Worker's satisfaction has a positive effect on workers commitment.

Figure 2: conceptual model

3. RESEARCH DATA AND METHOD

The study conducted in Kerala. Kerala is popularly known as the city of loom and lores town of export excellence, due to its unending relation with handloom industry. The handloom sector is significant source of the employment in Kerala, ranking second only to the coir sector among traditional industries in terms of employment. The industry is predominantly controlled by the cooperative sector, which accounts for 98.4 percent of the total looms.

3.1 Measurement scale:

The measurement items for this study were selected following a thorough literature review of previous research up to January 2024. All items have been validated in previous studies and are measured using Rensis' the 5-point Likert scale, which ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

4. RESULT AND DATA PROCESSING METHOD

The study employed SPSS for basic analysis and Smart PLS for advanced analysis. The first stage involved conducting Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to verify validity and reliability. The second stage focused entirely on 'Structural Equation Modelling' (SEM).

4.1 'Measurement model':

Figure 3: Author's Model

The 'Standardized Root Mean Square Residual' (SRMR) value for this model is 0.023, indicating the average absolute standardized difference between observed and predicted covariances. Typically, an SRMR value should be less than 0.08, indicating a good fit. Additionally, the structural model has a Normed Fit Index (NFI) of 0.937, which is above the recommended threshold of 0.9. The Chi-square value is 210.203. Overall, these metrics suggest that the model is a good fit.

Path coefficient value of workers training with workers satisfaction and workers commitment are 0.944 and 0.312. The R² value of workers satisfaction is 0.892 and workers commitment is 0.954. So, the workers training will create a positive effect on the workers satisfaction and workers commitment in handloom weaving cooperative society.

If the training provided to workers in the handloom weaving cooperative society is accurate and effective, the workers will not only contribute to the organization's success but also experience personal development. Ultimately, this will lead to increased commitment to their work.

Table 1: Construct reliability and validity

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
MC	0.952	0.953	0.952	0.800
MS	0.952	0.953	0.952	0.800
MT	0.959	0.960	0.959	0.825

Reliability and validity are crucial for assessing research the quality, reflecting how effectively the method, technique, or test measure something. Reliability pertains to the consistency of a measure, while the validity relates to its accuracy (Janssen, E. & et al 2017). Construct reliability is typically assessed using composite reliability and Cronbach’s alpha.

In this study, the variables examined are workers’ training (T), workers’ satisfaction (S), and workers’ commitment (C). ‘Cronbach’s Alpha’ was employed to assess internal consistency the reliability, evaluating the relatedness of items within each variable and construct. The values range between 0 and 1, with a threshold of 0.7 for reliability. Here, all variables have values above 0.8, indicating strong reliability. Composite reliability (rho_a & rho_c) values are also close to 1, further confirming high reliability and internal consistency.

‘Average Variance Extracted’ (AVE) was utilized to evaluate the convergent validity, with typical values exceeding 0.5. In this study, all variables have AVE values exceeding 0.5, representing satisfactory convergent validity. These factors collectively indicate that the measurement model is acceptable.

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	MC	MS	MT
MC	-		
MS	0.829		
MT	0.725	0.755	-

Discriminant validity is an essential concept in psychometrics and structural equation modelling that ensures distinct constructs or factors are indeed unique and not overly correlated with each other. In your dataset, we have three constructs: MC, MS, and MT, with correlation values of 0.829, 0.725, and 0.755 between them, respectively. While the correlations are moderately high, they do not exceed the threshold typically considered problematic (0.85 to 0.90), indicating that the constructs retain their distinctiveness. To further assess discriminant validity, one can compare the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct with the inter-construct correlations. The square root of the AVE should be greater than these correlations, confirming that each construct measures a unique aspect without significant overlap. Based on the provided data, the constructs demonstrate acceptable discriminant validity, indicating that the measurement model accurately represents different aspects of the concept being studied, with each construct contributing uniquely and distinctly. This validation is crucial for ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the constructs in the context of your research.

Table 3: Testing the Hypothesis, R2 Value, F2 Value and VIF

Hypothesis	Relationship	β	P value	Decision	R ²	F ²	VIF
H1	WT->WC	0.285	0.000	ACCEPTED	0.727	2.231	1.919
H2	WS->WC	0.060	0.000	ACCEPTED	0.954	1.087	2.342
H3	WT->WS	0.472	0.000	ACCEPTED	0.891	1.251	1.00

In Hypothesis 1 (H1), the path coefficient between workers' training (WT) and workers' commitment (WC) is 0.312. Hypothesis testing results in accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis, indicating that WT positively affects WC. The R^2 value for WC is 0.727, and the F^2 value is 2.231, suggesting an excellent global fit index. The 'variance inflation factor' (VIF) is 1.919, which is below the threshold of 3, suggesting that there are no multicollinearity issues. When workers' training positively impacts workers' commitment, it leads to the development of both individuals and the organization.

In Hypothesis 2 (H2), the path coefficient between workers' satisfaction (WS) and workers' commitment (WC) is 0.677. Hypothesis testing results in accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis, indicating that WS positively affects WC. The R^2 value for WC is 0.954, and the F^2 value is 1.087, suggesting an excellent global fit index. The 'variance inflation factor' (VIF) is 2.342, which is lower than the threshold of 3, suggesting that there are no multicollinearity issues. When workers' satisfaction positively influences their commitment, it fosters the growth and development of both the individuals and the organization.

In Hypothesis 3 (H3), the path coefficient between workers' training (WT) and workers' satisfaction (WS) is 0.944. Hypothesis testing results in accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis, indicating that WT positively affects WS. The R^2 value for WS is 0.891, and the F^2 value is 1.251, suggesting an excellent global fit index. The 'variance inflation factor' (VIF) is 1.00, which is below the threshold of 3, indicating no multicollinearity issues. When workers' training enhances their satisfaction, it promotes the growth and development of both the individuals and the organization.

5. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATION FOR MANAGERIAL ACTION

Training programs play a pivotal role in empowering weavers and enhancing their commitment to handloom weaving cooperative societies. By improving skills, fostering innovation, and providing financial education, these programs can significantly uplift the socio-economic status of weavers. Moreover, the support from government schemes ensures that these initiatives are sustainable and far-reaching. Ultimately, a well-trained and committed workforce can drive the growth and success of handloom weaving cooperative societies, preserving this traditional craft, and improving the livelihoods of millions of weavers.

Given the positive relationship between effective training and workers' satisfaction and commitment, managers should prioritize implementing comprehensive training programs that address both technical and personal development needs. This can improve product quality and enhance job satisfaction, ultimately fostering a more committed workforce. Additionally, creating a supportive and engaging work environment is crucial; managers should focus on regular feedback, recognition, and career growth opportunities to bolster job satisfaction and commitment. Allocating adequate resources and ensuring proper infrastructure, such as modern equipment

and quality raw materials, can further support training initiatives. Monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of these programs through performance metrics and regular assessments will help managers make necessary adjustments. Aligning HRM practices with organizational strategies, such as linking training programs to performance appraisals and career development plans, can enhance the overall effectiveness of these initiatives. Collaboration with government agencies, NGOs, and industry experts can provide additional support and resources, ensuring the sustainability and impact of training programs. By implementing these managerial actions, handloom weaving cooperatives can enhance organizational performance and support the economic and social development of their communities.

6. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION AND UNIQUE CONTRIBUTION

The study on empowering weavers through training on workers' commitment in handloom weaving cooperative societies offers several managerial implications. Managers should prioritize the implementation of comprehensive training programs that enhance both technical and soft skills, improving product quality and overall efficiency. Such training programs should be tailored to the specific needs of the weavers and include continuous learning opportunities. By fostering a supportive and engaging work environment, managers can increase job satisfaction and organizational commitment, ultimately driving better performance. Regular feedback, recognition, and career growth opportunities are essential for creating a positive workplace culture. Additionally, ensuring adequate resources and infrastructure, such as modern equipment and quality raw materials, is crucial for supporting effective training and employee development.

The unique contribution of this study lies in its empirical evidence demonstrating the positive impact of workers' training on their satisfaction and commitment within the context of handloom weaving cooperative societies. The findings highlight the significant role of training in enhancing organizational performance and personal development. By linking training programs to performance appraisals and career development plans, managers can align HRM practices with broader organizational strategies. This study also underscores the importance of collaboration with government agencies, NGOs, and industry experts to provide additional support and resources, ensuring the sustainability and effectiveness of training programs.

7. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study is limited by the sample size may not be representative of all handloom weaving cooperative societies in Kerala, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings. Moreover, the study heavily depends on self-reported data from participants, which can introduce bias and impact the accuracy of the results. The training programs' effectiveness might also vary significantly based on the individual characteristics of the weavers, such as their prior experience and educational background, which the study may not fully account for. Furthermore, the study's timeframe might be too short to observe long-term impacts of the training on workers'

commitment. Lastly, external factors such as market conditions and government policies, which can significantly influence the handloom sector, might not be adequately controlled, or considered in the study. However, the study has certain limitations that need to be addressed. The findings are based on data collected from a specific region (Kerala), which may limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or countries. Additionally, the study relies on cross-sectional data, which provides a snapshot of the current state but does not capture the long-term impact of training on worker satisfaction and commitment. Future research should consider longitudinal studies to assess the sustained effects of training programs over time. Expanding the study to include diverse regions and different types of handloom weaving cooperatives can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issues and barriers faced by the sector.

8. FUTURE SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The future scope of the study on empowering weavers through training on workers' commitment in handloom weaving cooperative societies is vast and multifaceted. One potential area for future research is the longitudinal assessment of the long-term impacts of training programs on workers' satisfaction, commitment, and overall productivity. By tracking changes over several years, researchers can gain deeper insights into the sustained effects of training and identify areas for continuous improvement. Additionally, expanding the geographic scope to include diverse regions across India and even other countries with significant handloom industries can provide a broader understanding of the issues and barriers faced by weavers globally. Further research could also explore the integration of advanced technologies and digital tools in training programs. Investigating how digital platforms, e-learning modules, and virtual workshops can enhance the training experience and accessibility for weavers in remote areas could yield valuable insights. Moreover, examining the role of government policies and initiatives in supporting training programs and their impact on the handloom sector's growth and development would be beneficial. Comparative studies that analyze the effectiveness of different policy interventions across regions can help identify best practices and inform policy-making.

Another important area for future research is the exploration of gender dynamics within handloom weaving cooperatives. Understanding the specific challenges faced by women weavers and the impact of training programs on their empowerment and economic independence can provide valuable insights. Researchers can also investigate the socio-cultural factors that influence worker commitment and satisfaction, offering a more holistic view of the factors that contribute to the success of handloom weaving cooperatives. Collaboration with industry stakeholders, including designers, marketers, and retailers, can also be explored to understand how training programs can be aligned with market demands and trends. This can help cooperatives better market their products, increase sales, and improve the livelihoods of weavers.

Lastly, studies focusing on the environmental sustainability of handloom weaving practices and how training can promote eco-friendly techniques and materials would be valuable. By addressing these future research areas, the study on empowering weavers

through training can significantly contribute to the sustainability and growth of the handloom industry, ensuring that it continues to thrive and preserve its rich cultural heritage.

9. CONCLUSION

The study highlights the critical role that worker training plays in enhancing both satisfaction and commitment among employees in handloom weaving cooperative societies. These training programs are not just about imparting technical skills related to handloom weaving but also include personal development aspects that foster a positive work environment. When workers receive comprehensive training that is specifically designed to meet their needs, they feel more competent and valued, leading to higher job satisfaction.

This satisfaction translates into a greater commitment to their work and the organization, creating a loyal and motivated workforce. A supportive work environment is crucial in this context. Managers must focus on providing the necessary resources, such as modern equipment, quality raw materials, and safe working conditions. These resources enable workers to perform their tasks efficiently and effectively, reducing frustration and enhancing job satisfaction. Additionally, fostering a culture of recognition and continuous feedback helps workers feel appreciated and motivated, further strengthening their commitment to the cooperative. The findings of the study are significant for HRM practices in the handloom sector, as they offer actionable insights for managers. By implementing effective training and development strategies, managers can directly improve organizational performance.

These strategies should be aligned with the broader organizational goals to ensure that training programs contribute to the overall mission and vision of the cooperative. For example, linking training programs to career development plans and performance appraisals can help create a clear path for workers' growth and advancement, enhancing their long-term commitment to the organization. Addressing the limitations of the study and expanding future research is essential for a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the success of handloom weaving cooperatives. Future studies could explore the long-term effects of training programs, include diverse geographic regions, and consider different types of cooperatives to provide a broader perspective. Such research would help identify best practices and innovative strategies that can be applied across the sector, ultimately supporting the economic and social development of rural communities.

The study emphasizes the importance of tailored training programs, supportive work environments, and strategic HRM practices in enhancing worker satisfaction and commitment. These elements are crucial for the success and sustainability of handloom weaving cooperative societies. By addressing the identified challenges and leveraging the study's insights, cooperatives can foster a motivated and skilled workforce, contributing to their growth and the preservation of cultural heritage.

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